

Kinetics of Reaction between Phthalic Acid and Potassium Peroxydisulphate-Part I.*

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The reaction has been carried out in H_2SO_4 medium in the presence of $AgNO_3$ as catalyst. The reaction is first order w.r.t. $[S_2O_8^{2-}]_0$ and zero order w.r.t. [phthalic acid] but the rate constant decreases with an increase in $K_2S_2O_8$ concentration, according to the relationship

$$-\log k = 2.65 + 13.33 [S_2O_8^{2-}]_0$$

The rate is only slightly increased on increasing the concn. of H_2SO_4 , while there is great increase with the increase in $AgNO_3$ concentration, the rate expression being of the form

$$\frac{dx}{dt} = kC_{Ag^+} \times C_{S_2O_8^{2-}}$$

The reaction is characterised by a low energy of activation (6.0 Kcals/mole), abnormally low frequency factor ($0.2708 \text{ litre mole}^{-1} \text{ sec.}^{-1}$) and a large negative entropy of activation (-28.390 E.S.U.). A yellow product soluble in acetone, glacial acetic acid, hot ethyl alcohol and in sodium hydroxide was obtained which chars and does not give any sharp m.p. The separation of the different reaction products by paper chromatography or by T.L.C. has not been successful so far.

Peroxydisulphate ion is known to act as a fairly powerful oxidising agent and has been successfully employed to bring about the oxidation of many classes of organic compounds. The kinetics of some of these oxidation processes has been studied by previous workers. Thus the oxidation of oxalic acid, formic acid, alcohols, aldehydes and ketones have been studied previously and these studies have recently been reviewed by House¹. Peroxydisulphate ion, besides behaving as an oxidising agent is also known to act as an initiator of polymerisation in aqueous solutions and emulsions². In the oxidation of phenols by peroxydisulphate ion in the presence of $AgNO_3$, Bacon, Grime and Munro³ found that polyphenols constitute almost the entire mass. The products obtained by the oxidation of aromatic carboxylic acids by peroxydisulphate ion^{4,5} frequently simulate those formed by Kolbe electrolysis. Thus O-benzoylbenzoic acid yields fluorenone and biphenyl-2-carboxylic acid affords 3,4-benzocoumarin⁵.

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1. D. A. House, *Chem. Rev.*, 1962, **62**, 185.
2. Evans and Baxendale, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1946, **42**, 197,
Nozaki and Bartlett, *J. Polymer Sci.*, 1948, **3**, 216,
Eager and Winkler, *Can. J. Res.*, B, 1948, **26**, 527,
3. R. G. R. Bacon, R. Grime and D. J. Munro, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 2275.
4. R. H. Thomson and A. G. Wylie, *Proceedings of Chemical Society* 1963, 65.
5. J. Russell and R. H. Thomson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1962, 3379,

The object of the present investigation is to study the kinetics and mechanism of the hitherto unstudied reaction between peroxydisulphate ion and phthalic acid.

EXPERIMENTAL

Potassium peroxydisulphate Analar B.D.H. was used after recrystallization and drying at room temperature under vacuum. Its standard solution was made daily by direct weighing of the recrystallised salt. The strength of the solution was verified by iodometric method. Phthalic acid E. Merck, G.R. was used and its standard solution was prepared by direct weighing of the acid. Other chemicals used were either of Analar quality or were used after recrystallisation.

Redistilled water from a pyrex distilling still was always used for making up the solutions.

Preliminary experiments showed that the reaction in the absence of a catalyst was very very slow even above 50° . However, in the presence of AgNO_3 as catalyst the reaction proceeds with measurable velocity at 55° . Therefore, the reaction was carried out at 55° in the presence of AgNO_3 as catalyst.

The reaction was carried out by running in calculated volume of $\text{K}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_8$ solution into the reaction vessel containing the other reactants, immersed in a thermostatic water bath with an accuracy of $\pm 0.1^{\circ}$. The progress of the reaction was studied by estimating the unreacted $\text{K}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_8$ by the iodometric method of Szabo, Csanyi and Galiba⁶, as modified by Khulbe and Srivastava⁷.

RESULTS

Since the self decomposition of peroxydisulphate ion at this temperature is appreciable in the presence of the catalyst the rate of self decomposition was studied simultaneously and the rate of disappearance of $\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}$ due to phthalic acid was evaluated by subtracting the rate constants of self decomposition from the observed value of rate constant.

- | | |
|---|---|
| 1. $\text{K}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_8 = 0.0025M$, | 4. $\text{K}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_8 = 0.0125M$, |
| 2. $\text{K}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_8 = 0.0075M$, | 5. $\text{K}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_8 = 0.0150M$, |
| 3. $\text{K}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_8 = 0.0100M$, | 6. $\text{K}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_8 = 0.0175M$. |

6. Szabo, Csanyi and Galiba, *Z. anal. Chem.*, 1952, **135**, 269.

7. K. C. Khulbe and S. P. Srivastava, *Proc. Nat. Acad. Sci.*, 1961, **30**, 117.

Further it was seen that a yellowish precipitate separates out after some time. However, it was found that the precipitate formation could be prevented for the major part of the reaction if it was carried out in the presence of sulphuric acid (0.1M). Hence the entire kinetic study reported below was carried out in H₂SO₄ medium.

1. *Effect of K₂S₂O₈ concentration*: The results obtained with six different initial concentrations of K₂S₂O₈ (from 0.0025M to 0.0175M) and the same concentrations of phthalic acid, AgNO₃ and sulphuric acid are shown graphically in figure 1 and the rate constant values are summarised below (Table No. 1).

TABLE 1

Phthalic acid = 0.03M		Temperature = 55°.		
H ₂ SO ₄ = 0.10M				
AgNO ₃ = 0.001M				
S.N.	K ₂ S ₂ O ₈ conc.(M)	k ₁ × 10 ³	k ₂ × 10 ³	(k ₂ - k ₁) × 10 ³
1.	0.0025	5.11004	7.18430	2.07426
2.	0.0075	4.57950	6.31820	1.73870
3.	0.0100	4.49510	6.14140	1.64630
4.	0.0125	4.18030	5.68650	1.50620
5.	0.0150	3.95760	5.30450	1.34690
6.	0.0175	3.86036	5.15770	1.29734

k₂ = specific rate in presence of phthalic acid.

k₁ = Specific rate in absence of phthalic acid.

It is seen that at all the concentrations of peroxydisulphate ion studied, the reaction is first order with respect to peroxydisulphate ion concentration. In any particular run the first order behaviour is maintained for the major part of the reaction studied (vide fig. 1). However, the first order rate constant decreases with an increase in the initial concentration of S₂O₈²⁻. A similar behaviour has been reported by Eager and Winkler in the oxidation of mercaptans (*loc. cit.*), by Srivastava and Ghosh⁸ in the oxidation of formate ion and by Khulbe and Srivastava⁹ in the Ag⁺ catalysed oxidation of isopropyl alcohol by K₂S₂O₈. Since the reaction has been carried out at fairly high ionic strength (in the presence of 0.1M—H₂SO₄) the most probable cause of this fall in rate constant may be due to the specific inhibitory effect of K⁺.

The relationship between $-\log k$ and [S₂O₈²⁻]₀ is linear (vide fig. 2). Where k is the specific rate constant for phthalic acid oxidation i.e., (k₂ - k₁) and [S₂O₈²⁻]₀ is the initial

8. S. P. Srivastava and S. Ghosh, *Z. Physik. Chem.*, 1953, **202**, 198.

9. K. C. Khulbe and S. P. Srivastava, *Agra Univ. J. Res. (Sci.)*, 1965, **XIV**, Pt. III, 125,

peroxydisulphate ion concentration. The slope of the curve is 13.33 and intercept is 2.65 and hence an equation of the type

$$-\log k = 2.65 + 13.33[S_2O_8^{2-}]_0$$

seems to be applicable.

- I. $AgNO_3 = 0.0005M$,
- II. $AgNO_3 = 0.0010M$,
- III. $AgNO_3 = 0.0015M$,
- IV. $AgNO_3 = 0.0020M$,
- V. $AgNO_3 = 0.0025M$.

2. *Effect of phthalic acid concentrations* : The rate constants corresponding to different initial concentrations of phthalic acid are summarised below in Table 2.

TABLE 2

$K_2S_2O_8 = 0.010M$
 $AgNO_3 = 0.001M$
 $H_2SO_4 = 0.100M$

Temperature = 55°

S.No.	Phthalic acid conc.(M)	$k_2 \times 10^3$	$(k_2 - k_1) \times 10^3$
1.	0.010	5.9709	1.4758
2.	0.015	5.9758	1.4807
3.	0.020	5.9737	1.4786
4.	0.025	5.9688	1.4737
5.	0.030	6.1414	1.6463
6.	0.035	6.0923	1.5972

The above data show that the rate is unaffected by a change in phthalic acid concentration and that the reaction is zero order with respect to phthalic acid concentration because the overall reaction is first order when carried out at equimolar concentrations of the reactants.

3. *Effect of $AgNO_3$ concentration* : The results obtained in presence of different concentrations of $AgNO_3$ as catalyst are represented in fig. 3 and the values of rate constant evaluated are given in Table 3.

TABLE 3

$K_2S_2O_8 = 0.01M$ $H_2SO_4 = 0.10M$ Phthalic acid = 0.03M		Temperature = 55°		
S.No.	$AgNO_3$ conc.(M)	$k_1 \times 10^3$	$k_2 \times 10^3$	$(k_2 - k_1) \times 10^3$
1.	0.0005	3.1386	4.3796	1.2410
2.	0.0010	4.4951	6.1414	1.6463
3.	0.0015	5.7563	8.3133	2.5570
4.	0.0020	8.1567	11.1679	3.0112
5.	0.0025	10.7170	14.8100	4.0930

From these data it is clear that the rate constant increases in a linear manner with an increase in $AgNO_3$ concentration. Thus the reaction obeys a rate expression of the form

$$\frac{dx}{dt} = kC_{Ag^+} \times C_{S_2O_8^{2-}}$$

4. *Effect of H_2SO_4 concentration* : The following set of results depict the effect of variation of H_2SO_4 concentration on the rate of reaction. It is seen that the rate of reaction increases only slightly with an increase in sulphuric acid concentration.

TABLE 4

$K_2S_2O_8 = 0.010M$ $AgNO_3 = 0.001M$ Phthalic acid = 0.030M		Temperature = 55°		
S.No.	H_2SO_4 conc.(M)	$k_1 \times 10^3$	$k_2 \times 10^3$	$(k_2 - k_1) \times 10^3$
1.	0.100	4.4951	6.1414	1.6463
2.	0.125	4.2729	6.1303	1.8674
3.	0.150	3.5681	5.5068	1.9387
4.	0.200	2.6168	4.6845	2.0677

5. *Effect of temperature* : In order to evaluate energy parameters the reaction was

carried out at four different temperatures, the results for which are tabulated below :

TABLE 5

Sl. no.	Temp. °C	$k_1 \times 10^3$	$k_2 \times 10^3$	$(k_2 - k_1) \times 10^3$	Temp. coeff.	Energy of activation K.cal./mole	Frequency factor litre/mole sec.	ΔS^\ddagger E.S.U.		
		$K_2S_2O_8 = 0.010M$				$AgNO_3 = 0.001M$				
		$H_2SO_4 = 0.100M$				Phthalic acid = 0.030M				
1.	55	4.4951	6.1414	1.6463	}	}	0.27121	-28.432		
2.	60	7.4866	9.3718	1.8852			1.29	5.6	0.27040	-28.393
3.	65	9.2649	11.3840	2.1191			1.33	6.4	0.26583	-28.375
4.	70	12.097	14.6000	2.503					0.27581	-28.362
				Mean	1.31	6.0	0.27081	-28.390		

It is seen that the reaction is characterised by a low energy of activation and has an abnormally low value of frequency factor. This suggests that the formation of the activated complex involves either a separation of opposite charges or an approach of like charges¹⁰. It may be pointed out that such a low value of frequency factor and energy of activation, although not reported in any of the other Ag^+ catalysed redox reactions of peroxydisulphate ion has, however, been observed by us in the oxidation of benzoic acid by $S_2O_8^{2-}$ ¹¹ under similar conditions. The value of the energy of activation and frequency factor for the different Ag^+ catalysed reactions of $S_2O_8^{2-}$ vary greatly. However, the first order behaviour of this reaction with respect to $[S_2O_8^{2-}]$, zero order with respect to phthalic acid (organic substrate), linear dependence of rate on $[Ag^+]$ and decrease in the rate constant with an increase in $[S_2O_8^{2-}]$ suggests that probably this reaction also follows the same general mechanism as suggested for other Ag^+ catalysed reactions. Thus the initial reactions may be as follows :

The $SO_4^{\cdot-}$, OH and OH^+ radicals may be then attacking phthalic acid to give the different products.

Isolation and identification of reaction product : Equimolar concentrations (M/20) each of $K_2S_2O_8$ and phthalic acid were kept at room temperature. $AgNO_3$ (0.001M) was used as catalyst. The reaction proceeds very slowly. The whole mixture is allowed to stand for nearly 72 hr. till the yellow product formed settles down. It is filtered under

10. K. J. Laidler, *Reaction Kinetics*, Vol. II, p. 24.

11. Paper read at the 6th Annual Convention of Indian Chemical Society held at Ahmedabad 1968 and communicated for publication in *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*

pressure and dried at room temperature. It is aromatic in nature and chars with concentrated sulphuric acid. It is soluble in acetone, hot alcohol, glacial acetic acid while in sodium hydroxide solution it dissolves giving reddish brown solution. It gives test for carboxyl group with NaHCO_3 dissolving partly in it. The product is, however, insoluble in ether, petroleum ether and sparingly soluble in benzene. On heating it does not melt but the product darkens in colour above 100° and swells up later on and finally a black residue is left.

Paper chromatography of the substance dissolved in acetone was carried out in ethanol: ammonia: water (80 : 4 : 16) system, when the product was observed to move with the solvent front without giving a definite spot. Various spraying reagents e.g., $\text{FeSO}_4 + \text{K}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_8$, alcoholic solution of methyl red, iodate-iodide, universal indicator and alcoholic iodine solutions were tried but without success. However, the substance on a glass strip coated with silica gel in (60% $\text{CHCl}_3 + 40\%$ CH_3OH) and kept in benzene gave a reddish brown wave on exposure to iodine vapour. This substance on similar treatment also gave a brownish black wave with concentrated sulphuric acid. Thus the separation of the different polymeric products by chromatographic technique could not be effected.

The details of the mechanism can only be worked out after a complete analysis of the product (s), which is being attempted by various techniques. Besides this, the effect of dielectric constant, of substituents and of ionic strength and the mole-ratio are being investigated to enable us to formulate a detailed reaction mechanism of this reaction.

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